

Newsletter 10 / 2022

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Save the date

6th Workshop on Coupling Technologies for Earth System Models

The 6th Workshop on Coupling Technologies for Earth System Models (CW2023) will be held on January 18-20, 2023 in Toulouse, France. The workshop will be held in a hybrid format with remote attendance possible. The workshop aims to bring together leading researchers and practitioners in the field of coupling infrastructure for Earth System Models. This workshop is the sixth in the series, started in 2010 in Toulouse and followed by Boulder USA (2013), Manchester UK (2015), Princeton USA (2017) and virtual (2020). You can register by filling [this form](#). Details on the workshop will be updated regularly on the [workshop webpage](#).

This workshop is funded by the EU H2020 [IS-ENES3](#) project and co-organised by Cerfacs and Argonne National Laboratory.

Spread the word

Newly published success story: Exploring interoperability between DSLs

Domain-specific languages (DSLs) allow scientists to port their model codes more easily to new hardware, and they also facilitate optimisation and parallelisation on different machines.

However, why would anyone need more than one DSL for a single application domain such as climate modelling?

Read our new success story to find out how and why ESIWACE researchers have successfully combined the two DSLs PSyclone and DAWN, achieving interoperability. [Read the story here](#). (Photo source: pexels.com)

ECMWF will organise a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) early next year

The banner features a blue background with a globe on the right side, overlaid with a network of white and green lines representing data connections. The ECMWF logo is in the top left, and the iFAB logo is in the top center. The main title 'MOOC Machine Learning in Weather & Climate' is prominently displayed in white text. Below the title, it says 'Register now for our FREE online course'. At the bottom left, the University of Luxembourg Competence Centre logo is visible.

ECMWF
EUROPEAN CENTRE FOR MEDIUM-RANGE WEATHER FORECASTS

in partnership with
iFAB
INTERNATIONAL FOUNDATION
FOR DATA AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
FOR HUMAN DEVELOPMENT

MOOC Machine Learning in Weather & Climate

Register now for our **FREE** online course

University of Luxembourg
Competence Centre

ECMWF will organise a massive open online course on Machine Learning in Weather & Climate. The free registration is already open. This is a great opportunity if you want to learn about the topic with no need to have previous knowledge. Please help to spread the word. <https://moodle.ecmwf.int/pages/index.htm>

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [SC22](#), Dallas, TX (USA), 13-18 November, 2022
- [IEEE Vis 2022](#), Oklahoma City, OK (USA), 15-22 October, 2022
- [ESiWACE2 Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling](#), online, 7 October, 2022
- [iCAS 2022](#), Stresa (IT), 11-15 September, 2022
- [Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation](#), online, 6-9 September, 2022
- [UMAP2022](#), Monterey, CA (USA), 25-29 July, 2022

News & updates

ESiWACE2 Second Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling successfully completed

This workshop organised in the context of ESiWACE2 under the lead of CMCC was successfully held as a virtual event on 7 October 2022. Donatello Elia (CMCC) opened the workshop floor and the session chairs (Erwan Raffin (ATOS), Andrew Porter (STFC) and Peter Dueben (ECMWF)) guided participants through the virtual programme that saw 14 speakers presenting in three different tracks:

- European Exascale Hardware
- Programming models and hardware interplay
- Machine learning

Although being virtual, the workshop was successful with a lot of attendees in each track and lively Q & A parts at the end of the presentation slots. About 132 participants from 22 countries all over the world had registered to attend, with the highest number of registrations from Germany, UK, Italy, France and the USA.

All talks were delivered live in a videoconference and, given that the speakers agree, will be published on the [ESiWACE YouTube channel](#). Stay tuned for those and for the presentation slides to be added to the [workshop agenda](#)! Read also our website [news item](#) on the workshop.

Several ESiWACE2 Partners contributing to Destination Earth’s Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin

ECMWF has announced that an international partnership led by [CSC](#), the host institution of the pre-exascale supercomputer [LUMI](#), will deliver the Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin as part of the implementation of [Destination Earth](#), the flagship initiative of the European Commission.

Several ESiWACE partners, namely BSC, MPI-M and DKRZ, are part of the consortium. The core of the Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin will be constituted by a new generation of two model systems that have been supported as ESiWACE2 flagship models: **ICON** from a joint venture between the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M), the German

Meteorological Service Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) and the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), and ECMWF’s **Integrated Forecasting System (IFS)** coupled to the **NEMO** ocean model developed by the NEMO Consortium and, alternatively, to the German Alfred Wegener Institute’s **FESOM** ocean model.

Read ECMWF’s full announcement here:

<https://stories.ecmwf.int/finlands-csc-leads-international-partnership-to-deliver-destination-earths-climate-change-adaptation-digital-twin/index.html>

3rd ESIWACE2 Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation

CMCC and DKRZ held a third and final virtual training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation within the scope of ESIWACE2. In four 2-hour online sessions from 6 to 9 September 2022 the training attendees learned the ropes of HPDA and visualisation using Ophidia, PyOphidia and ParaView.

The 2022 training course had 53 registrations (22 females, 28 males, 3 decided to not respond) from 17 countries worldwide with Germany, Romania, Italy, France, UK and the USA being the most represented countries. Registrations mainly came from academia or research centres, with more than half of the registered attendees being early career scientists or students.

Material on Ophidia: <https://github.com/ESiWACE/hpda-vis-training/tree/master/Training2022>

Material on ParaView: <https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/visualization/sw/paraview/Examples/index.html>

To revisit the training content, please have a look at the [recording of last year's HPDA & visualisation training](#) on YouTube.

In-situ visualisation and analysis of ICON data at IEEE VIS 2022

The [2022 edition of IEEE VIS](#), a major international conference for scientific visualisation, information visualisation and visual analytics, was held as a hybrid event from 16 to 21 October in Oklahoma City, USA.

In the associated 12th IEEE Symposium on **Large Data Analysis and Visualization (LDAV)**, ESIWACE staff member Nils-Arne Dreier (DKRZ) gave an Early Career Researcher Lightning talk. His presentation addressed the progress made and

the challenges encountered in working on in-situ visualisation and the analysis of very large output data from simulations with a high-resolution version of the global climate model ICON.

More information: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events/ieee-vis-2022>

Recently published ESIWACE2 Deliverables and Milestones

In the last months we released the following three ESIWACE2 deliverables:

D6.2: Report on different trainings

D6.2 is the summary report on all training courses in pre-exascale HPC software engineering, methods and tools applied to the domain of weather and climate modelling that were conceptualised and delivered in the scope of the second funding phase of ESIWACE. The report contains details on all training courses completed at the time of publication and covers course contents, links to training material and anonymised information on participant statistics and satisfaction survey results. [Read D6.2 here](#)

D5.2: Report on the implementation of the ESDM PAV analytical kernels for post-processing, analysis and visualisation

D5.2 reports on the implementation and testing of the analytical kernels for post-processing, analysis and visualisation (PAV). This deliverable describes the analytical kernels, i.e. the core routines for PAV applications selected and developed in the context of ESIWACE2 work package 5 to show the interplay with the ESDM. These analytical kernels make use of GPUs and streaming I/O APIs (for in-flight analytics) and have been designed and developed to exploit novel computing architectures and I/O technologies with the goal of improving PAV applications, and have been integrated with CDO and Ophidia. [Read D5.2 here](#)

D4.2: Report on appliances available for testing

Deliverable D4.2 builds on [D4.1](#), “Advanced software stack for Earth system data“, which documents the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) I/O library and its application for workflows and use cases. In the recently published D4.2, storage technology vendors and ESIWACE partners DDN and SEAGATE report on two storage technologies designed to work with the ESDM. Seagate demonstrate the capability of CORTX Motr to work with ESDM on commodity hardware, and DDN the relevance and the efficiency of ESDM on state-of-the-art industrial storage technologies. [Read D4.2 here](#)

Snapshots

Atos Bull

Atos finished the Service 1 projects dealing with the OGSTM and BLOM models and focused on deliverable D3.2. Service 3 activity on weather and climate benchmarking is moving forward: HPCW v2 is on the way and deployment on different HPC systems is ongoing.

BSC

Autosubmit 4 (Python3 version, new YAML-based config system) has already passed the first testing phase and is now finishing the second one. Interoperability with LUMI is going to be verified in the next few weeks.

CERFACS

As planned in WP3, CERFACS provided OASIS3-MCT Dedicated Support to the UK Met Office. That work allows the coupled model UKESM to adopt a degraded resolution coupling, based on the OASIS3-MCT-based solution previously implemented in NEMO-PISCES, but using the MEDUSA BGC model instead.

CMCC

CMCC, together with DKRZ, organised in September the third online training on HPDA & Visualisation, providing an updated set of training materials for the HPDA sessions. Moreover, CMCC organised, jointly with the program committee and the support from DRKZ, the ESIWACE2 Second Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling. Finally, the performance evaluation of the Ophidia extensions for in-flight analytics using the ESDM API has continued, as well the testing of the integration within the ESDM-PAV interface.

DDN

Jointly with partner SEAGATE, DDN has completed the work on Deliverable D4.2, “Report on appliances available for testing”.

DKRZ

In WP5, we have further improved the prototype for in-situ visualisation YAVIZ and its interface to the ICON model. Now, more variables can be captured from the running simulation and an algorithm for tetrahedralisation is implemented, which allows for efficient volume rendering of 3D data. Moreover, we have delivered the third and final edition of the HPDA & visualisation training together with CMCC.

At the project office, we have supported the ESIWACE2 Second Virtual Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling, and are ramping up our efforts to promote and disseminate ESIWACE results, and to finalise the project at the end of March 2023.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

Together with partners from U-Reading, ETH/C2SM, and BSC, we are currently working hard on the final M2.8 deliverable of containerised earth science models, namely LFRic, COSMO, EC-Earth and ICON. Thanks to the project extension, we will hand in our deliverable for review at the end of December.

Seagate

Seagate is working closely with DKRZ to deploy CORTX Motr on the test system there and also to explore possibilities for continued collaboration with the weather and climate community post the end of the project.

News from the neighbors

Modelling team reaches technical milestone: global Earth system simulations at 1.2 km resolution

A team of modelling experts from the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M) and DKRZ has succeeded at meeting a “grand challenge” formulated a decade ago: developing a global climate model that resolves convective-scale motions (nominally around 1 km horizontal resolution), opening the door for researchers to investigate local impacts of climate change with a new class of global numerical models.

Using the recently installed new supercomputer “Levante” at the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ), the modellers have, for the first, demonstrated that it is technically possible to run a 3D coupled global version of

the ICON-based Earth system model at 1.2 km horizontal resolution in both atmosphere and ocean. The development was achieved within the scope of projects WarmWorld and nextGEMS and will contribute to Destination Earth (DestinE). (Image credit: Florian Ziemer / DKRZ)

Read the full news article of our partner institute MPI-M here:

<https://mpimet.mpg.de/en/communication/news/single-news/technical-milestone-reached-global-earth-system-simulations-with-12-km-resolution>

IS-ENES3 Central & Eastern Europe Autumn School: From Climate Projections to Climate impacts via Regional Downscaling: 28 November - 2 December 2022, Prague (Czech Republic)

[Charles University](#), Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Atmospheric Physics, within the project

IS-ENES3, with cooperation of [KNMI](#) and the [Faculty of Physics of Belgrade](#), organises two parallel schools (with common days to CORDEX FPC Convection final General Assembly) targeted to climate and impact researchers from Central and Eastern Europe on 28 November until 2 December 2022 in Prague (Czech Republic).

Climate change is one of the biggest challenges of our times. To be able to conduct climate change impact studies and to adapt to climate change, understanding the climate system's behaviour - especially in higher resolution, considering local conditions - is essential, and knowledge on climate data and experience in processing and analysing climate data is needed. The main source of future data are climate projections, and we rely on regional downscaling for high resolution information.

During the school, climate and impact researchers and students will get lectures on climate models and downscaling methods, on tools to analyse and process climate data and how to apply them for impact studies. This is combined with information on where and how to access the necessary data, as well as dedicated time for tutorials and practical exercises in order to get experience with these data and tools. Special occasion is given to participants to attend the final meeting with selected presentations of CORDEX FPS Convection (to be held last three days of the schools), where they can get acquainted with the up-to-date activity in dynamical downscaling in very high resolution, so-called convection permitting access to the modelling, describing convection explicitly without parameterisation.

You can apply before November 7th via the application form available on the [event official webpage](#).

IS-ENES3 Newsletter - September 2022 issue

In September our partner project [IS-ENES3](#) released its latest newsletter issue. Read it [here](#).

Open positions

DKRZ is hiring a [Software Engineer / Scientific Programmer \(all genders\) for HPC Applications](#) to work on adapting and optimising climate models for Europe's largest and most advanced supercomputers as part of an international team and within the projects Destination Earth and ESiWACE3. Apply before 18 November 2022!

The project ESiWACE2 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823988.